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POTENTIALS OF AGROECOLOGICAL PRACTICES IN EAST AFRICA WITH A FOCUS ON CIRCULAR WATER-ENERGY-NUTRIENT SYSTEMS

D3.3 – Report on expansion of agroecological indicators to cover integrated aqua-agriculture (IAA) food production systems in East Africa

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Abstract	<p>This report details the development of Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) indicators to assess sustainability, aiming to comprehensively evaluate economic, environmental, and social dimensions. These indicators offer standardized metrics for comparing IAA systems across regions, species, and time frames. Employing desktop reviews and structured questionnaires, indicators were selected and validated through workshops in Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. Findings reveal predominant private ownership (80%) of IAA farms, with production varying from commercial to community levels. Average fish yields range from 500-1000 kg per hectare, with significant water recycling practices (over 70%) and integration of fish-pond crop systems (over 85%), primarily with vegetables. Investment in IAA, mainly within the \$5,000 to \$20,000 range, focuses on infrastructure and technology. Influential factors include market price, production costs, and supportive policies. This insight into East Africa's IAA sector highlights opportunities for addressing challenges and leveraging policies to enhance food security, economic growth, and environmental sustainability.</p>
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Agroecological indicators have been developed to assess the sustainability of agricultural systems by considering environmental, social, and economic dimensions. However, in recent years, there has been growing recognition of the potential of Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) practices to enhance sustainability. The objective of this task was to develop IAA-specific indicators. Developing indicators of sustainability to assess Integrated IAA systems is important for several reasons. It allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of aquaculture systems. This holistic approach will help understand these systems' overall sustainability performance. Also, indicators provide a standardized and quantifiable way to measure and compare different IAA systems. Using indicators makes it possible to assess and compare the sustainability of systems across different regions, species, and time scales. IAA indicators were selected based on desktop reviews and field data collection using structured questionnaires. The results were then validated through co-creation workshops in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania by capturing the views and opinions of the various stakeholders. More than 80% of the integrated aqua agriculture (IAA) farms are privately owned, a mode which is reported to work better when ponds are under group ownership with less than 5% of the respondents indicating government ownership in the three countries. The scale of production varies from large-scale (commercial level) to medium-scale (community level). The study shows variation in average fish yield per hectare in the range of 500-1000 kg. Water consumption for aquaculture varies as well, with a significant proportion falling under low and moderate consumption categories. More than 70% of the farmers implement water recycling and conservation practices. Over 85% of the farms sampled integrate fish-pond crop systems, with vegetables being the most commonly integrated crop. Total investment in IAA varies, across East Africa with a substantial proportion falling within the \$5,000-\$20,000 range. Infrastructure constitutes a significant portion of investment, followed by technology and operational costs. The factors reported to influence gross margins were market price, production costs, and supportive policies. This information provides valuable insights into the status and characteristics of IAA across East Africa. Addressing challenges and leveraging supportive policies can further enhance the growth and impact of the IAA sector in East Africa, contributing to food security, economic development, and environmental sustainability.

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ABBREVIATIONS

IAA	Integrated Agriculture Aquaculture
ABDP	Aquaculture Business Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme

DEFINITION OF TERMS

a. Technology

Technology is defined as an output of a research process which is beneficial to the target clientele (mainly farmers, pastoralists, agro-pastoralists, and fisher folk for KCSAP's case). A technology can be commercialized and can be patented under intellectual property rights (IPR) arrangements. Examples include research outputs such as tools, equipment, genetic materials, improved fish breeds, new vaccines, new equipment, laboratory techniques, etc.

b. Innovation

This is defined as a modification of existing technology for an entirely different use from the original intended use. It is also an application of new or existing knowledge/technology in a new way or context to do something better or different. An example is a narrow-deep lined or cemented pond for rearing catfish.

c. Management Practices

Management practice is defined as recommendation(s) on practice(s) that is/are considered necessary for a technology to achieve its optimum output. These include, for example, different agronomic practices (e.g., seeding rates, fertilizer application rates, spatial arrangements, planting period, land preparation and watering regimes), protection methods for crops, and feed rations, management systems, and disease control methods, etc. for livestock breeds. This is therefore important information which is generated through research to accompany the parent technology before it is finally released to users and the technology would be incomplete without this information.

1. INTRODUCTION

Integration of crops and animals is considered important for the sustainable development of agriculture distinguished three pathways to achieve agricultural development [1], [2]. These include (i) intensification, increasing the cultivated area while maintaining or decreasing farm inputs per hectare; (ii) intensification, increasing farm production per hectare through increased inputs and mechanization (iii) diversification, integration of farm subsystems and products for improved social, environmental and economic sustainability. One form of diversification is the integration of agriculture and aquaculture systems (IAA). IAA is defined as “concurrent or sequential linkages between two or more agricultural activities (one or more of which is aquaculture), directly on-site, or indirectly through off-site needs and opportunities, or both” [3][4].

FIGURE 1: POSSIBLE ON-FARM INTERACTIONS BETWEEN IAA COMPONENTS (MODIFIED FROM EDWARDS ET AL., 1988).

Traditional agricultural practices have often been associated with negative ecological impacts, such as soil degradation, water pollution, and loss of biodiversity [5]. Agroecological indicators have been developed to assess the sustainability of agricultural systems by considering environmental, social, and economic dimensions. However, in recent years, there has been growing recognition of the potential of Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) practices to enhance sustainability [6].

Developing indicators of sustainability to assess Integrated Agriculture-Aquaculture (IAA) systems is important for several reasons. It allows for a comprehensive evaluation of the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of aquaculture systems. This holistic approach helps understand these systems' overall sustainability performance [3]. Also, indicators provide a standardized and quantifiable way to measure and compare different IAA systems. Using indicators makes it possible to assess and compare the sustainability of systems across different regions, species, and time scales.

Furthermore, indicators help in incorporating science-based knowledge into decision-making processes. They provide valuable information for policymakers, farmers, and other stakeholders to make informed choices and take actions that promote sustainable aquaculture practices. Lastly, the development of indicators of sustainability helps to move away from subjective or convention-based approaches and instead focuses on objective and measurable criteria. This enhances transparency, credibility, and accountability in assessing and promoting sustainable IAA practices.

A. Enhancing Resource Efficiency

IAA practices involve the integration of crop production and aquaculture within the same system, allowing for synergistic interactions and resource sharing. By combining agriculture and aquaculture, IAA practices have the potential to improve resource efficiency. For example, the nutrient-rich effluents from aquaculture can be utilized as fertilizers for crop production, reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers [7]. Including IAA practices in sustainability indicators acknowledges the resource-saving potential of these integrated systems.

B. Diversification of Production

Incorporating IAA practices in sustainability indicators recognizes the importance of diversifying production systems. IAA allows for the cultivation of multiple crops and fish species within the same system. This diversification enhances the resilience of food production by reducing the risks associated with monocultures. Diverse IAA systems can provide a range of nutritious foods, contribute to food security, and reduce vulnerability to market fluctuations [8].

C. Ecological Benefits

IAA practices can offer ecological benefits by promoting ecosystem functions and biodiversity conservation. The combination of aquaculture and agriculture can create habitats that support a greater diversity of plant and animal species. Wetlands, constructed within IAA systems, provide feeding and breeding grounds for various organisms, contributing to the overall ecological health of the system [9]. Including IAA practices in sustainability indicators recognizes their potential to support ecosystem services and maintain biodiversity.

D. Social and Economic Dimensions

Sustainability indicators should not only consider ecological aspects but also encompass social and economic dimensions. IAA practices have the potential to improve the livelihoods of rural communities by providing additional income opportunities and diversifying their sources of food and nutrition [10]. By integrating agriculture and aquaculture, IAA systems can generate employment, foster local entrepreneurship, and enhance food sovereignty. Including IAA practices in sustainability indicators ensure a comprehensive assessment of the social and economic benefits they offer.

The development of indicators of sustainability that include Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) practices is essential for a holistic evaluation of agricultural and aquacultural systems. By recognizing the resource efficiency, diversification of production, ecological benefits, and social and economic dimensions associated with IAA, these indicators provide a more comprehensive understanding of the sustainability of food systems. It is crucial to adopt an integrated approach that considers the interconnections between agriculture and aquaculture to promote sustainable and resilient food production systems for the future.

2. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT.

The purpose of this document is to provide information on how specific indicators for Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) systems were developed, recognizing their potential to enhance sustainability. By evaluating economic, environmental, and social dimensions, these indicators offer a holistic understanding of IAA systems' sustainability performance. Standardized and quantifiable, they facilitate comparisons across regions, species, and time frames, enabling a comprehensive assessment of sustainability. These indicators were meticulously selected based on desktop reviews and structured questionnaires, with validation through stakeholder workshops in Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania. Findings reveal significant trends in IAA ownership, production scales, fish yields, water consumption, and farming practices across East Africa. Understanding these dynamics provides valuable insights into the status and characteristics of IAA, informing strategies to address challenges and leverage supportive policies. Ultimately, this endeavour aims to foster the growth and impact of the IAA sector in East Africa, contributing to food security, economic development, and environmental sustainability.

A. METHODOLOGY

The methodology involved a combination of top-down and bottom-up methods to develop a set of indicators for assessing the sustainability of different aquaculture systems, especially for the East African context. The indicators were developed based on discussions with experts, farmers, and other stakeholders, as well as data collected from different production systems. The indicators were then reviewed and selected based on their feasibility, universality, and ability to assess the sustainability of different IAA systems. Finally, the indicators were validated at co-creation workshops and through field data collection for different systems and species. The methodology followed here is based on [11].

2.2.1 Selection the indicators

The indicators will be developed using a combination of top-down and bottom-up methods, combined with practical observations in experimental and commercial aquaculture facilities. The development process will involve the following steps:

1. Conducting a literature review of existing studies on aquaculture sustainability indicators. This will help identify the key indicators that have been used in the past and the gaps that need to be addressed. The review was based on published journal articles, grey literature, and project reports retrieved from various databases like Google Scholar, The Lens.org, Dimensions AI, Scopus and more. The review took into consideration keywords related to sustainability, aquaculture, and IAA.
2. Identifying key stakeholders and experts in the field and engaging them in discussions to identify relevant criteria and indicators was done. The stakeholder and experts included researchers, fisheries and aquaculture managers, farmers, marketers and distributors, those in value addition and more. These discussions were conducted through a combination of in-person meetings and online surveys. This included the use of Key Informant Interview Guides, Focus Group Discussions and structured questionnaires.
3. Developing a list of criteria: A list of criteria relevant to the sustainability of aquaculture systems was developed. These criteria covered economic, environmental, and social aspects of sustainability.
4. Indicator selection: The selection was based on feasibility, ease of obtaining, universality, clarity, and broad applicability.
5. Developing a list of indicators: Based on the criteria we identified in step 3, we developed a list of indicators that can be used to assess the sustainability of aquaculture systems. These indicators were quantitative and measurable.
6. Validation: The indicators were then validated by collecting data from different production systems, on farms and on research stations and through co-creation workshops conducted in Kenya, Uganda and Tanzania. The data collected was used to test the feasibility and validity of each proposed indicator.
7. Compiling the indicators: The indicators were then compiled into a comprehensive portfolio and reviewed with stakeholders and experts to ensure their relevance and usefulness.

2.2.2 Field data collection

For the field data collection, questionnaires were developed and then digitized using KOBO Collect. Surveys were subsequently conducted on Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) farms identified across Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania during the T2.2 mapping process. The aim was to gather comprehensive data on various aspects of IAA practices and operations. This approach provided valuable insights into the implementation and characteristics of IAA systems in East Africa, contributing to a deeper understanding of their dynamics and sustainability. The data collected was analysed and discussed in the context of East Africa.

2.2.3 IAA Indicators Identified and validated

i. Economic indicators

The economic indicators were further divided into four categories: production, profitability, employment, and value chain. The production indicators include gross production, production per unit area, production per unit of feed, survival rate, and feed conversion ratio. The profitability indicators included gross income, net income, profit margin, and return on investment. The employment indicators included labour productivity and employment. The value chain indicators include gross value added and market share.

Production indicators	
	1. Gross production (F)
	2. Production per unit area (F)
	3. Production per unit of feed (F)
	4. Survival rate (F)
	5. Feed conversion ratio (F)
Profitability indicators	
	6. Labor productivity (F)
	7. Gross income (F)

	8. Net income (F)
	9. Profit margin (F)
	10. Return on investment (F)
Employment indicators	
	11. Gross value added (R)
	12. Employment (R)
	13. Value chain (S)
	14. Market share (S)

In the indicators, R, F, and S refer to the different scales at which the indicators can be applied:

- R: Regional scale

- F: Farm scale

- S: Sectorial scale

These scales are used to indicate the level at which the indicators can be applied, depending on the context and purpose of the assessment. For example, some indicators may be more relevant at the farm level, while others may be more relevant at the regional or sectorial level.

ii. Environmental Indicators

The environmental indicators are divided into six categories: water quality, effluents, energy, biodiversity, chemicals, and waste. The water quality indicators include dissolved oxygen, ammonia, nitrite, nitrate, total suspended solids, biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, and total phosphorus. The effluent indicators include carbon footprint, energy use, water use, organic matter, solid waste, and liquid waste. The biodiversity indicators include biodiversity, habitat alteration, and introduction of non-native species. The chemical indicators included chemicals, antibiotics, pesticides, and heavy metals.

Water Quality Indicators	
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	1. Dissolved oxygen (F)
	2. Ammonia (F)
	3. Nitrite (F)
	4. Nitrate (F)
	5. Total suspended solids (F)
	6. Biochemical oxygen demand (F)
	7. Chemical oxygen demand (F)
	8. Total phosphorus (F)
	9. Total nitrogen (F)
Effluent Indicators	
	10. Carbon footprint (S)
	11. Energy use (S)
	12. Water use (S)
	13. Organic matter (F)
	14. Solid waste (F)
	15. Liquid waste (F)
Biodiversity Indicators	
	16. Biodiversity (R)
	17. Habitat alteration (R)
	18. Introduction of non-native species (R)
Chemical Indicators	
	19. Chemicals (R)
	20. Antibiotics (R)

	21. Pesticides (R)
	22. Heavy metals (R)

NOTE: In the indicators, R, F, and S refer to the different scales at which the indicators can be applied:

- R: Regional scale
- F: Farm scale
- S: Sectorial scale

These scales are used to indicate the level at which the indicators can be applied, depending on the context and purpose of the assessment. For example, some indicators may be more relevant at the farm level, while others may be more relevant at the regional or sectorial level.

iii. Social indicators

The social indicators are divided into four categories: labour, community, food security, and animal welfare. The labour indicators include employment, gender equity, income distribution, education, health, community participation, and access to services. The community indicators include food security, animal welfare, occupational health and safety, child labour, and forced labour. The food security indicators included social responsibility, social license to operate, human rights, community development, social capital, social cohesion, social inclusion, and indigenous peoples.

Labor indicators	
	1. Employment (F)
	2. Gender equity (R)
	3. Income distribution (R)
	4. Education (R)
	5. Health (R)
	6. Community participation (R)

	7. Access to services (R)
Community Indicators	
	8. Food security (R)
	9. Animal welfare (F)
	10. Occupational health and safety (F)
	11. Child labor (F)
	12. Forced labor (F)
	13. Social responsibility (S)
	14. Social license to operate (S)
	15. Human rights (S)
	16. Community development (S)
	17. Social capital (S)
	18. Social cohesion (S)
	19. Social inclusion (S)
	20. Indigenous peoples (S)

NOTE: In the indicators, R, F, and S refer to the different scales at which the indicators can be applied:

- R: Regional scale
- F: Farm scale
- S: Sectorial scale

These scales are used to indicate the level at which the indicators can be applied, depending on the context and purpose of the assessment. For example, some indicators may be more relevant at the farm level, while others may be more relevant at the regional or sectorial level.

2.2.4 Co-creation workshops for validation of the indicators

One-day validation workshops were organized in Kenya, Tanzania, and Uganda, led by MSU, SAT, and UMU in the respective countries. These workshops aimed to validate and verify the IAA indicators identified and described through desktop review. The co-creation workshops brought together diverse stakeholders including farmers, financial institution representatives, government extension officers, researchers, and policymakers, to collaborate on the validity, practicality and applicability of the IAA indicators identified in the desktop analysis. Stakeholders' expertise and perspectives were leveraged to refine the development of the indicators, recognizing them as crucial end users. During the workshops, stakeholders provided opinions and suggestions to integrate their feedback into the IAA indicators and description of the Technologies, Innovations and Management Practices (TIMPs).

2.2.5 Linking Indicators to Technologies Innovations and Management Practices (TIMPs)

The indicators were then linked to various Technologies Innovations and Management Practices (TIMPs) that are deemed relevant for the East African region.

3. INTEGRATED AQUACULTURE SYSTEMS

TABLE 1: RECIRCULATING AQUACULTURE SYSTEMS (RAS)

TIMP name	Solar/Wind-Powered Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS)
Category (i.e., technology, innovation or management practice)	Innovation
A: Description of the technology, innovation, or management practice	
Agroecological problems being addressed	Water scarcity due to climate change and competition for available water resources is a concern in food production systems. Food and nutrition insecurity especially among smallholder farmers particularly in urban and peri urban areas and the high cost of energy in food is a challenge in production systems.
TIMP description	<p>Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) are closed and semi-closed systems that intensively cultivate fish and reuse a large proportion of treated culture water to reduce water consumption and the release of nutrients into the environment. In a RAS system (Figure 1), water for fish rearing is reused after a cleaning and a filtering process.</p>

Justification	RAS are designed to optimize space and water use and to reduce wastewater discharge thus reducing environmental contamination. The systems reduce water consumption by up to 90-99% and allow greater control over environmental and water quality conditions. By removing waste (e.g., uneaten food, excrement, and dead bacteria), RAS improve conditions for cultured fish, enhancing feeding efficiency and allowing for higher stocking densities than most aquaculture systems. Besides, the systems provide market benefits such as the ability to match seasonal supply and demand and to co-locate production with consumer demand and supply patterns.
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TABLE 2: AQUAPONIC SYSTEMS

TIMP name	Aquaponics systems
Category (i.e., technology, innovation or management practice)	Innovation
A: Description of the technology, innovation or management practice	
Agroecological Relevance of the Innovation	Fish excrete waste containing nutrients that affect water quality but are beneficial to plant growth.
TIMP description	<p>Aquaponics is the integration of recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) and hydroponics in one production system. In an aquaponic unit, water from the fish tank cycles through filters, plant grow beds and then back to the fish. In the system, water flows from the fish tank into a biofilter where bacteria break down the fish waste into an organic nutrient solution for the growing vegetables. The plants then absorb the nutrients from the water which essentially cleans it before being re-circulated back into the fish tanks (Figure 2).</p> <p>Figure 2: Process of aquaponic operation (Source: Piccolo et al. 2019)</p>

	<p>Aquaponics at NARDTC KMFRI Sagana</p>
Justification	<p>Aquaponics is a recirculating food production system that uses less than 10% of the water normally required for fish farming and plant production. Therefore, it is suitable for small-scale/domestic consumption as well as commercial organic food production, particularly in communities where water is scarce. There is very little water loss due to evaporation and plant transpiration. High-priced organic produce can be produced for urban markets, for instance. Aquaponics systems conserve water and plants growing in these systems grow quicker, larger and with a higher yield (15%) than those growing in a regular hydroponics system.</p>

TABLE 3: INTEGRATED MULTITROPHIC AQUACULTURE (IMTA)

TIMP name	Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA)
Category (i.e., technology, innovation or management practice)	Innovation
A: Description of the technology, innovation or management practice	
Agroecological problems addressed by the Innovation	Low fish production and productivity and the environmental pollution associated with cage aquaculture systems especially from uneaten feeds and fish wastes.
TIMP description	Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture aims at the integrated production of aquaculture species of different trophic levels under a circular economy approach, minimizing energy losses and environmental deterioration

<p>Justification</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IMTA allows the creation of more sustainable production systems because wastes of fish/shrimp production are valued as a resource rather than considered a burden or pollution. This contributes to environmental sustainability and a more efficient use of resources while favoring economic diversification (product diversification, bringing company stability through risk reduction), and social acceptability (best management) • Integrated multi-trophic aquaculture has additionally been recognized as a contributor to reducing public opposition toward intensive aquaculture

TABLE 4: RICE-FISH CULTURE SYSTEMS

<p>TIMP name</p>	<p>Rice-fish culture systems</p>
<p>Category (i.e., technology, innovation or management practice)</p>	<p>Innovation</p>
<p>A: Description of the technology, innovation or management practice</p>	
<p>Agroecological problem addressed by the innovation</p>	<p>For increased food production, there is need for vast tracts of land for rice cultivation and water bodies for fish cultivation, which is very limited in Kenya with population of close to 50 million. Due to</p>

	<p>lack of enough technical knowledge and training on improved rice-fish culture, which is expanding every day, many farmers are not getting optimum results in production.</p>
<p>TIMP description</p>	<p>A rice-fish system is an integrated rice field or rice field/pond complex, where fish are grown concurrently or alternately with rice. Fish may be deliberately stocked (fish culture) or may enter fields naturally from surrounding water ways when flooding occurs (rice field fisheries), or a bit of both. Fish yields can range widely from of 1.5 to 174 kg/ha/season depending on the type of rice fish system, the species present, and the management employed.</p>
<p>Justification</p>	<p>Due to limited land and water resources in Kenya, it is necessary to use same plot of land in multiple ways. Rice-fish culture is the system of cultivation of different crops in the same field at the same time, where the maximum use of land is ensured while maintaining ecological balance and achieving economic benefit. Moreover, by dyke cropping there are opportunities for farmer to fulfill nutritional demand of the family as well as an opportunity to earn excess money.</p>

TABLE 5: CROP-LIVESTOCK FISH SYSTEMS

<p>TIMP name</p>	<p>Crop-Livestock-Fish Systems</p>
<p>Category (i.e. technology, innovation or management practice)</p>	<p>Innovation</p>

A: Description of the technology, innovation or management practice	
<p>Agroecological problem addressed by the innovation</p>	<p>Due to water scarcity and the gradual shrinking of land holdings in most East African countries, it is essential to integrate land-based enterprises such as crops, poultry, livestock, and horticultural crops within the bio-physical and socio-economic environment of fish farming. There is low adoption and application of integrated crop, livestock and fish technologies despite many decades of research and development programs.</p>
<p>TIMP description</p>	<p>Integrated farming is the “concurrent or sequential linkages between two or more human activity systems, one or more of which is aquaculture, directly on-site, or indirectly through off-site needs and opportunities, or both”. The basic idea of crop-livestock-fish (CLF) is that wastes from other activities (e.g., crop residues, livestock manure and by-products) are used as feed/pond fertilizer, and fish wastes are recycled back into the system to fertilize crops.</p> <div data-bbox="616 913 1406 1512" data-label="Diagram"> </div>

Justification	Integration of crops, livestock and fish (CLF) holds considerable potential for augmenting production of high-value animal protein, generation of employment opportunities and improvement of socio-economic conditions of rural small holder farmers. An output from one subsystem in an integrated farming system, which otherwise may have been wasted, becomes an input to another subsystem resulting in a greater efficiency of output of desired products from the land and water under a farmers' control thus increasing farmers' food and income security.
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4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS OF FIELD DATA ON IAA INDICATORS

In the survey, respondents were distributed across Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania, Table 1 indicates that 30 respondents were from Uganda, accounting for 39% of the total respondents.

TABLE 6: DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS

Country	Count	Proportion
Kenya	42	55%
Tanzania	5	6%
Uganda	30	39%
Total	77	100%

In this study, it was reported that the majority (80%) of integrated aqua agriculture (IAA) farms across the three countries are privately owned (Fig. 2). The scale of production varies from large-scale (commercial level) to medium-scale (community level). This suggests a diverse landscape of ownership and production scales within the IAA sector within the region. Private ownership might dominate due to various factors such as ease of establishment, autonomy in decision-making, and potentially greater access to resources. Privately owned fish farms have been reported to work better than when ponds are under group ownership as reported by [12]. In Kenya, there was a significant number of community owned farms which could be attributed to the recognition and encouragement of group and community farms by programmes like the Aquaculture Business Development Programme (ABDP).

FIGURE 2: FARM OWNERSHIP

The prevalence of fish-pond crop integration among the respondents across the region indicates a significant interest in utilizing fish ponds alongside crop cultivation, potentially due to the complementary benefits each system offers. This approach allows for efficient use of resources, such as water and nutrients, and promotes sustainable farming practices [13]. Another reason may be the ease of construction and the low capital costs associated with the ponds. The smaller representation of aquaponics and fish tank crop integration across the three countries could be attributed to the high initial capital requirement for the systems making them beyond the reach of most smallholder farmers within the region. The most prevalent type of integration is fish-pond crop systems, with vegetables being the most commonly integrated crop across the three countries. The integration of vegetables such as Chinese cabbage, cabbage (*Brassica spp.*), and amaranth (*Amaranth spp.*) with ponds offers significant benefits. These vegetables have short cultivation cycles and high marketability, and their cultivation is sustained by the nutrient-rich water from fish ponds during water-scarce periods, ensuring a continued source of income and essential vitamins for households, this was also reported by [14]. Crop farming practices vary as reported in the study, with a significant proportion implementing occasional rotation and succession planning for both crop and fish. Soil management predominantly leans towards organic practices, indicating a preference for sustainable and environmentally friendly methods.

FIGURE 3: TYPE OF IAA INTEGRATION

Scale of operation

Regarding the scale of operation (Figure 4), the majority of respondents engaging in small-scale (backyard) operations reflects the prevalence of subsistence farming and smallholder agriculture in the region. Small-scale farming is often a primary means of livelihood for many rural households, offering opportunities for self-sufficiency and income generation at a local level. The limited representation of medium-scale and large-scale operations could be attributed to various factors, including access to capital, infrastructure, and market opportunities [14]. Limited access to resources and challenges in accessing formal markets might hinder the scalability of operations beyond the small-scale level for many farmers in the East African region.

FIGURE 4: SCALE OF OPERATION

Integrated Aquaculture-Agriculture (IAA) systems play a significant role in shaping the agricultural landscape across the East African region, with each system exhibiting unique characteristics that influence fish yield, water consumption, recycling practices, and pollution mitigation measures (Table 7). In Uganda for example, over 50% of surveyed farms reported fish yields of less than 500 kg/ha, indicating various challenges such as limited access to inputs or inadequate infrastructure. In contrast, approximately 20% of farms achieved yields between 500-1,000 kg/ha, while around 27% surpassed 1,000 kg/ha, showcasing the potential for higher productivity with effective management and favorable conditions. In Tanzania and Kenya, the study shows variation in average fish yield per hectare, with the majority falling within the range of 500-1000 kg. This implies a moderate performance, where the community demonstrates a moderate level of fish farming productivity. While yields may not reach the upper limits of what is possible with optimal management and resources, they still fall within a range that can contribute significantly to local food security and economic viability for the local smallholder farmers [15].

Water management is crucial in aquaculture, as highlighted by the varying water consumption patterns observed among surveyed farms. In Uganda, majority (36.7%) reported daily water consumption exceeding 1,000 liters, emphasizing the significance of efficient water use. Water consumption for aquaculture varies (but generally lower) in Kenya and Tanzania with a

significant proportion falling under low and moderate consumption categories. However, a high proportion of respondents across the three countries implement water recycling and conservation practices, indicating a growing awareness of sustainable water management within the sector. Interestingly, more than 70% of farms implementing recycling and conservation practices utilized low or moderate amounts of water, demonstrating the effectiveness of such strategies in optimizing water usage and minimizing environmental impact. However, the importance of water quality cannot be overstated in aquaculture farming systems. It is reassuring that 90% of surveyed farms have implemented strategies to mitigate pollution, indicating a collective effort to safeguard water quality. Pollution in aquaculture farms can have detrimental effects on aquatic ecosystems, fish health, and human consumers, underscoring the critical need for pollution prevention measures.

TABLE 7: CHARACTERISTICS OF THE VARIOUS IAA SYSTEMS ACROSS THE THREE COUNTRIES

Variables	Category	Country			Overall Proportion
		Kenya	Tanzania	Uganda	
Average fish yield per hectare	<i>500 - 1000 kg</i>	19	3	6	36.4%
	<i>Less than 500 kg</i>	17	-	16	42.9%
	<i>More than 1000 kg</i>	6	2	8	20.8%
		42	5	30	100.00%
Water consumption for Aquaculture	<i>High (more than 1000 liters per day)</i>	2	4	11	22.1%
	<i>Low (less than 500 liters per day)</i>	17	-	9	33.8%
	<i>Moderate (500 - 1000 liters per day)</i>	23	1	10	44.2%
		42	5	30	100.00%
Water recycling and conservation practices	<i>Implemented</i>	31	5	23	76.6%
	<i>Not implemented</i>	11	-	7	23.4%
		42	5	30	100.00%
Measures taken to prevent water pollution	<i>Not implemented</i>	6	-	3	11.7%
	<i>Occasionally implemented</i>	29	1	8	49.4%
	<i>Regularly implemented</i>	7	4	19	39.0%
		42	5	30	100.00%

Integration and IAA practices

Aquaculture systems across the three countries were observed to be diversified through integration with various crops, including vegetables, grains, fruits, and apiary. Figure 5 illustrates that the majority of farms integrated vegetables, followed by fruits and grains within their farming systems. The popularity of integrating vegetables, fruits, and grains can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, these crops often complement fish farming well, both in terms of resource utilization and market demand. Vegetables and fruits, for instance, can utilize excess nutrients from aquaculture ponds through hydroponic or aquaponic systems, promoting nutrient cycling and maximizing land use efficiency. Additionally, these crops are typically high-value products with consistent demand in local markets, offering farmers additional income streams and diversification opportunities. The integration of vegetables such as Chinese cabbage, cabbage (*Brassica* spp.), and amaranth (*Amaranth* spp.) with ponds offers significant benefits. These vegetables have short cultivation cycles and high marketability, and their cultivation is sustained by the nutrient-rich water from fish ponds during water-scarce periods, ensuring a continued source of income and essential vitamins for households, this was also reported by (Chenyambuga 2014). Crop farming practices vary as reported in the study, with a significant proportion implementing occasional rotation and succession planning for both crop and fish. Soil management predominantly leans towards organic practices, indicating a preference for sustainable and environmentally friendly methods. The integration with mangroves were observed mostly at the Kenyan coast.

FIGURE 5: TYPES OF CROPS INTEGRATED

Results in table 38 reveal various agroecological practices pertaining to crop farming in the three countries, showcasing the adoption and transition by farmers to agroecological practices across the region. Notably, regular crop rotation and succession planning for both crops and fish emerged as widely implemented strategies, emphasizing proactive management and resource optimization. In terms of irrigation methods, while flood irrigation was relatively common, more efficient techniques like drip irrigation were less frequently employed. This could be attributed to the amount of technological and financial requirements for the installation of these sophisticated irrigation methods. Surprisingly, a notable proportion of respondents reported not using any irrigation method, which may indicate reliance on natural rainfall patterns. This can have a negative impact on production especially due to the impacts of climate change. Organic soil management practices were predominant, with 90% of respondents favoring sustainable approaches. Conversely, practices such as mixed inorganic soil management and high-level integration of technology in crop farming were less commonly reported. This underscores the need for capacity building and awareness creation for smallholder farmers across the region on agroecology and IAA practices.

TABLE 8: IAA PRACTICES – CROP FARMING

Variable	Category	Country			Overall Proportion	
		Kenya	Tanzania	Uganda		
Crop rotation	<i>No rotation</i>	11		7	18	25.4%
	<i>Occasional rotation</i>	22	5	8	35	49.3%
	<i>Regular rotation</i>	4		14	18	25.4%
		37	5	29	71	100.0%
Succession planning for crop and fish	<i>Implemented</i>	19	5	21	45	66.2%
	<i>Not implemented</i>	15		8	23	33.8%
		34	5	29	68	100.0%
Irrigation method used	<i>Drip irrigation</i>	4		6	10	13.0%
	<i>Flood irrigation</i>	26	5	11	42	54.5%
	<i>Sprinkler irrigation</i>	5		2	7	9.1%
	<i>Watering cans</i>	3		8	11	14.3%
	<i>None</i>	4		3	7	9.1%
		42	5	30	77	100.0%
Soil management practices	<i>Inorganic</i>	1			1	1.3%
	<i>Mixed</i>	4	5	3	12	15.6%
	<i>Organic</i>	37		27	64	83.1%
		42	5	30	77	100.0%
	<i>High level</i>	2	1	7	10	13.0%

Integration of technology in crop farming	<i>Low level</i>	12		5	17	22.1%
	<i>Moderate level</i>	25	4	16	45	58.4%
	<i>None</i>	3		2	5	6.5%
		42	5	30	77	100.0%

Types of Aquaculture systems

Across the three countries, aquaculture farms were classified into two main categories: pond-based and recirculating systems. The majority of farms were are pond-based, where fish are raised in constructed earthen or liner ponds. Pond-based systems are commonly used due to their relatively low cost and simplicity, making them accessible to a wide range of smallholder farmers. In contrast, approximately 36% (Fig. 6) of farms utilize recirculating systems, which continuously filter and recycle water within a closed-loop system. Recirculating systems are known for their higher efficiency and ability to control water quality parameters, but they often require higher investment costs and technical expertise.

FIGURE 6: TYPES OF AQUACULTURE SYSTEMS

Infrastructure and Equipment

Investment in aquaculture infrastructure is paramount for the success of any fish production venture. Aquaculture infrastructure encompasses a wide range of components, including ponds, tanks, water supply systems, aeration equipment, and processing facilities. Results

from Figure 7 demonstrate that the majority of farms, accounting for invested in moderate-level aquaculture infrastructure with a moderate number of farms opting for basic infrastructure. Very few farms (<25%) invested in advanced infrastructure, which may include high-tech systems like recirculating aquaculture systems or automated energy and feed systems. This distribution underscores varying levels of investment and prioritization among aquaculture operators, with considerations such as budget constraints, scale of operations, and technological readiness influencing infrastructure decisions.

FIGURE 7: AQUACULTURE INFRASTRUCTURE AND EQUIPMENT

Energy Sources

At a farm level, the fish farming processes; that is, fish breeding with associated activities, transportation, and handling of grown fish, together with relevant activities such as feed processing; and at times processing and distribution to the customers, involve requirement for energy. The energy consumption and associated emissions, depend on the farming process and energy source. The sources of energy at the IAA farms in East Africa were majorly solar (61.8%), followed by grid electricity (31.46%) and lastly diesel generators (6.74%) as presented in Figure 8. The energy is required to operate pumps and filtration units, to heat the water especially in the fish hatcheries; and during processing and preservation of the harvest.

Reliance on solar energy is most preferred due to the unreliability and black outs associated with grid electricity, it’s a cheap renewable energy and is environmentally friendly. Once set-up little maintenance costs are incurred. Diesel or fuel generators were least used as a source of energy because the fuel is expensive, there is noise pollution and hence they are located remotely from the farms where they can easily be stolen. However, some farmers who owned diesel pumps used them for on-farm feed formulation, which ensured high quality feeds at a cheaper price. In addition, they are less environmentally friendly compared to solar and grid electricity. Grid electricity was used by a moderate proportion of farms but the frequent power cut-offs, inaccessibility especially in some rural areas propel some farmers to utilize other sources, either solely or in combination.

Energy intensity is not only a good indicator of environmentally unsound systems, but also of systems vulnerable to fluctuations in energy prices. Majority of the farmers used the renewable energy sources, which indicates that desirable AE practices are observed and that there are reduced energy expenses.

FIGURE 8: SOURCES OF ENERGY USED IN THE IAA SYSTEM

Measures for Energy Efficiency

Some of the processes which are energy consumption intensive include feed production and processing, water recirculation and maintaining temperatures in the fish production units. Plant-based ingredients have less impact on the environment compared to animal based (fish meal, fish oil and processing of animal co-products such as offals). High dependency on energy and greenhouse emissions may be variably associated with the different production systems, hence the need for application of energy efficient measures.

Across East Africa, some of the measures taken for energy efficiency included growing fish in green houses, exploitation of gravitational flow of turbid water to the sediment tank, feeding whole unprocessed plant materials and black soldier fly larvae and installation of solar panels for energy source. However, majority of the farmers partially (43.3%) or did not (23.3%) implement any of the measures and only 10 (33.3%) farms fully implemented the energy efficiency practices (Figure 9). Farms that implemented measure for energy efficiency are likely to have lower production costs and minimum effect on the environment.

FIGURE 9: MEASURES TAKEN FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY

Investment levels

There is increasing involvement in aquaculture production due to the high population growth that need to be fed, the demand for healthier protein sources and employment opportunities.

Investors in aquaculture are driven by the need to diversify their income sources, the potential stable returns and promising growth prospects of the sector. The magnitude of investment in IAA is mainly influenced by affordability and the type of fish production system. The East African region has great potential for developing aquaculture beyond small volume production models into larger commercial scale production operations using both cages and land-based systems for tilapia (cages) and catfish and tilapia (land-based ponds).

Total investment across the region was mainly under \$10,000 accounting for about 80% of the farms and the funds were used for infrastructure development, technology and operational costs (Table 9). Since majority of the farmers utilize pond culture of 50m² to 200m² with little or no technical inputs or management, this explains the proportion of farmers with the low investment (80%) and low technological costs (19.3%) that were reported in the current survey. The other forms of fish culture such as aquaponics and RAS, which need higher investment costs and technological inputs, are just coming up and are therefore not commonly encountered. With the drive to commercialize aquaculture, pond sizes of with surface area of ca. 500 m² have been set-up; and such farms have adopted use of inputs such as quality fish seed and feed, which are some of the operational costs in addition to labor, organic fertilizers, and lime required to cover a single production cycle. The high operational costs yet few farms invested in technology, is likely to affect the profitability of the enterprises.

TABLE 9: INVESTMENT LEVELS

Variable	Category	Country		
		Kenya	Tanzania	Uganda
Total Investment	\$5,000 - \$10,000	85.70%	40%	80%
	\$5,000 - \$10,001	2.40%		3.30%
	More than \$10,000	11.90%	20%	16.70%
		100%	100%	100%
Breakdown of Investment	a. Infrastructure	41.8%	60%	48.50%
	b. Technology	28.70%	25%	19.30%
	c. Operational costs	29.50%	15%	32.20%
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Factors influencing Gross Margins

Positive gross margins and net farm incomes are highly influenced by quantities and prices of the fish and other products sold, but this is thwarted by high production costs, which include the operation and fixed costs. The operation costs include fingerlings, fish feeds, organic manure, lime and labor while fixed costs include pond construction costs, seine nets, predator nets, and other assorted tools. However, when calculating for gross margin over a production cycle, depreciation on the fixed items is determined using equipment salvage value. Gross margin ratios (GMR) are calculated using gross margins divided by the revenues generated. In Kenya and Uganda for example, positive gross margins and GMR levels of 64.1% and 64.8% were previously observed, which indicate greater efficiency in turning fish sales into income [16]

The factors that influence gross margins were reported as production costs, market prices and policy by 56%, 42% and 2% of the IAA farmers, respectively (Figure 10). Having production costs as one of the factors influencing the gross margin is supported by previous reports of low return on investments. After production costs, the market prices were the next most frequently (42%) reported factor affecting gross margins. The low market prices are as a result of presence of capture fisheries, the low purchasing power of the community, and limited capacity to process and add value to fish which are highly perishable commodities.

Few IAA farmers (2%) presented policy as another factor influencing the gross margin. This indicates that either very few of the farmers are aware about the presence of various policies that in one way or another support performance and development of the sector. The farmers would benefit from such policies such as the NORAD and ABDP partnerships that advocate for research and foreign direct investment to introduce new technologies and innovations, elevate levels of sustainable production and quality of fish and aquaculture production. However, some of the global fisheries policies primarily focused on environmental and economic research agenda with less emphasis on regulating production, maintaining sustainable supplies and strengthening the role of fisheries in food security and economic development. The inadequate regulatory role, especially concerning the quality of fish feed and seed was of major concern to the IAA farmers.

FIGURE 10: FACTORS INFLUENCING GROSS MARGINS

Cost-benefit analysis

Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) for an aquaculture farm involves comparing the costs, both the initial start-up costs and on-going operational expenses, to the stream of revenues and other benefits that accrues over time. The analysis is used to measure the economic efficiency of allocating resources to meet certain human needs. The CBA helps the farmers or investors to make evidence-based decision to continue or undertake the IAA farming activities. Cost-benefit analysis was conducted by majority of the IAA farms (Table 10). This implies that the farmers have information relating to the economic performance of their enterprises. As usually experienced with most smallholder farmers, 40.7% of the IAA farms in the current survey reported not having cost-benefit analysis done, which is usually due to poor record keeping practices. Small-scale aquaculture enterprises are reported to be profitable but with small profit margins, which usually discourages the investors. Farmers need to be advised on undertaking the CBA to enable evaluation of the technologies and practices introduced on their farms, which will eventually help in identifying the most appropriate to promote for maximum profitability of the enterprises.

TABLE 10: COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Country	Conducted a cost-benefit analysis for the IAA system	Proportion
Kenya	36	
No	12	33.3%
Yes	24	66.7%
Tanzania	5	
Yes	5	100%
Uganda	27	
No	11	40.7%
Yes	16	59.3%
Grand Total	68	

Factors considered in the Cost-benefit analysis

The major factors considered in the Cost-benefit analysis were market trends, input costs and labour charges for both skilled and unskilled (Figure 11). Within the IAA practices, the farm inputs include; fertilizers, seeds (crops and fish), agro-chemicals, irrigation equipment, water flow piping infrastructure, feeds, fuel and services (e.g. purchase of the inputs, animal insemination). The labour force required include; crop field operations, animal grazing/feeding, fish feeding, pond water management, farm security, fish harvest and farm management. Some of the labourers are hired on a permanent basis and reside on the farm while others are drawn from the community when the need arises. Due to rural-urban migration in many areas, farm labour is generally expensive. Markets of farm produces are largely controlled by middlemen who give farmers low prices for their produces, yet the farmers incur high costs to raise the fish to maturity and other produces like animals and vegetables. To enhance their incomes, farmers have developed innovative marketing strategies of reaching either the final consumer or better markets. These include; i) making announcement on the local radio to inform buyers as to when the fish will be delivered to the trading centre/market stalls, ii) grading of the fish in different sizes where the small size (200-500 gm) are sold in the community and the bigger sizes (>500 gm) is sold in towns where the prices are higher, and iii) targeting regional fish markets.

FIGURE 11: FACTORS CONSIDERED IN THE COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Impact on household income

A majority of the respondents reported increased/stable household income which was attributed to investment in IAA (Figure 12). This is not surprising given that aquaculture is in general a huge investment in Uganda and these farmers could profit from the venture. These farmers also had explored better market opportunities to reach the final consumer, hence eliminating the middlemen. Many of these farms, benefitted from vertical integration (circular economy) of resources, whereby animal waste like manure would be used to raise vegetables which would be fed on the fish. Some farmers would use kitchen waste to raise maggots (from black soldier flies) which would be fed on the fish. The fish is degutted before they are sold, and the fish intestines are fed to pigs. These ventures bring financial stability to the farm.

FIGURE 12: IMPACT ON HOUSEHOLD INCOME

Employment generation within the community

Although aquaculture farms are largely big investments in the rural area, only 33% of the farms reported high employment creation in the area, while 40% of the farms report moderate employment creation (Figure 14). This is attributed to two factors; rural-urban migration of the work force and the general laziness trends among the youth. Young people are more interested in other service industries than agriculture, aquaculture inclusive.

FIGURE 13: EMPLOYMENT GENERATION WITHIN THE COMMUNITY

This report provides valuable insights into the status and characteristics of integrated aqua agriculture in the three East African counties. There are however variations in ownership, production scale, and practices, there is a common trend towards sustainability and profitability across the countries. Addressing challenges and leveraging supportive policies can further enhance the growth and impact of the IAA sector in Tanzania, contributing to food security, economic development, and environmental sustainability.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of Integrated Agri-Aquaculture (IAA) specific indicators through desktop reviews and structured questionnaires, validated in co-creation workshops across Kenya, Uganda, and Tanzania, underscores a vital step towards assessing the sustainability of aquaculture systems. These indicators offer a standardized means to comprehensively evaluate economic, environmental, and social dimensions of IAA systems, facilitating comparisons across regions, species, and timeframes. The study reveals that the majority of IAA farms are privately owned, with varying scales of production and considerable investment in infrastructure and technology. Notably, water conservation practices are prevalent, with integration of fish-pond crop systems, primarily featuring vegetables. Insights into factors influencing gross margins, such as market prices and production costs, highlight the complexities of IAA economics. Addressing challenges and leveraging supportive policies is crucial for the sector's growth and its potential contribution to food security, economic prosperity, and environmental sustainability in East Africa.

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APPENDIX A: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR T3.3 FIELD DATA COLLECTION

Guidelines: The tool is not supposed to replicate what has been done in T2.2 but to go deeper into some of the indicators advanced for IAA practices. These indicators will be identified in terms of assessment of the levels of socioeconomic, climate smartness and environmental indicators that can be benchmarked in typical sets of practices that represent particular IAA enterprise combinations (e.g. Tilapia/Vegetables) and technologies (e.g. RAS). The partners can agree on the details to define gaps and also on the number of IAA enterprises to reach out to.

Information gathering tool to assess/benchmark Integrated Aqua Agriculture (IAA) Systems/practices/technologies in East Africa

Section 1: General Information

1. Respondent Information:

- Name:
- Position/Occupation:
- Organization/Institution:
- Contact Information:
- GPS location

2. Location:

- Country:
- Region/Province:
- Specific Location (if applicable):

3. Type of ownership

- Private
- Community owned
- Government

Section 2: Integrated Aqua Agriculture (IAA) System Overview

4. Type of IAA System:

- Fish-pond Crop Integration
- Aquaponics
- Rice-Fish Farming
- Other (Specify):

5. Scale of Operation:

- Small-scale (Backyard)
- Medium-scale (Community)
- Large-scale (Commercial)
- Others (specify)

Section 3: Performance Assessment

6. Productivity and Yields:

- Average fish yield per hectare (specify the area of system):
 1. Less than 500 kg
 2. 500 - 1000 kg
 3. More than 1000 kg

7. Water Management:

- Water consumption for aquaculture:
 1. Low (less than 500 liters per day)
 2. Moderate (500 - 1000 liters per day)
 3. High (more than 1000 liters per day)
- Water recycling and conservation practices:
 1. Implemented
 2. Not implemented
- Measures taken to prevent water pollution:
 1. Regularly implemented
 2. Occasionally implemented
 3. Not implemented

8. Crop Varieties and Rotation:

- Types of crops integrated:
 1. Vegetables
 2. Fruits
 3. Grains
 4. None
 5. Others (specify)
- Crop rotation practices:
 1. Regular rotation
 2. Occasional rotation
 3. No rotation
- Succession planning for crops and fish:
 1. Implemented
 2. Not implemented

Section 4: Technology and Infrastructure

9. Aquaculture Technology:

- Types of aquaculture systems used:
 1. Recirculating
 2. Pond-based
 3. Other (Specify):
- Aquaculture infrastructure and equipment:
 1. Basic
 2. Moderate
 3. Advanced

10. Agriculture Technology:

- Irrigation methods used:
 1. Drip irrigation
 2. Sprinkler irrigation
 3. Flood irrigation
 4. Others (specify)
- Soil management practices:
 1. Organic
 2. Inorganic
 3. Mixed
- Integration of technology in crop farming:
 1. High level
 2. Moderate level
 3. Low level
 4. None

11. Energy Sources:

- Sources of energy used in the IAA system:
 1. Solar
 2. Grid electricity
 3. Diesel generators
- Measures taken for energy efficiency:
 1. Implemented
 2. Partially implemented
 3. Not implemented

Section 5: Economic/Financial Considerations

12. Investment Levels:

- Total investment made in establishing and maintaining the IAA system (which currency units to be used- Kshs, Ugshs, Tshs):
 1. Less than \$5,000
 2. \$5,000 - \$10,000
 3. More than \$10,000
- Breakdown of investment in terms of percentage of investment (e.g., infrastructure, technology, operational costs):
 1. Infrastructure
 2. Technology
 3. Operational costs

13. Gross Margins:

- Estimate of gross margins from the IAA system in the last financial year (2022 or 2023):
 1. Profitable
 2. Break-even
 3. Loss-making
- Factors influencing gross margins (e.g., market prices, production costs):
 1. Market prices

2. Production costs
3. Other (Specify)

14. Cost-Benefit Analysis:

- Conducted a cost-benefit analysis for the IAA system:
 1. Yes
 2. No
- Factors considered in the analysis (e.g., input costs, labor, market trends):
 1. Input costs
 2. Labor
 3. Market trends

Section 6: Challenges and Opportunities

15. Challenges Faced:

- Common challenges encountered in the IAA system:
 1. Lack of technical know-how
 2. Market access
 3. Input availability
 4. Others (specify)
- Any specific challenges related to the region:
 1. Yes
 2. No

16. Opportunities and Innovations:

- Opportunities for improvement and innovation:
 1. Collaborations or partnerships that have enhanced economic performance:
 2. Yes
 3. No

Section 7: Socioeconomic Impact

16. Income and Livelihoods:

- Impact on household income:
 - Increased
 - Stable
 - Decreased
- Employment generation within the community:
 - High
 - Moderate
 - Low

17. Community Engagement:

- Involvement of local communities in economic activities related to IAA:
 - Actively involved
 - Partially involved
 - Not involved
- Training and capacity-building initiatives with an economic focus:
 - Regularly conducted

- Occasionally conducted
- Not conducted

Section 8: Regulatory and Policy Environment

18. Regulatory Support:

- Support received from government agencies or local authorities:
 - Yes
 - No
- Regulatory challenges faced:
 - Yes
 - No

19. Policy Recommendations:

- Suggestions for improving policies related to the economic aspects of IAA:
 - Yes
 - No
- Desired policy changes to support sustainable economic practices:
 - Yes
 - No

Section 9: Future Outlook

20. Adoption Potential:

- Perception of economic benefits and adoption potential in the region:
 - High
 - Moderate
 - Low
- Factors influencing future economic sustainability:
 - Market trends
 - Government support
 - Climate resilience

21. Research and Development Needs:

- Identified economic research gaps or areas for improvement:
 - Yes
 - No
- Desired support for further economic development:
 - Financial support
 - Technical support
 - Policy advocacy